

Supplementary Information for

**Forage silica and water content control dental surface texture in guinea
pigs and provide implications for dietary reconstruction**

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Other supplementary materials for this manuscript include the following:

Dataset S1

Figure S1. Results of x-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis for the three fresh forages (milled plant powders) as well as lucerne mixed with an increasing percentage of quartz dust ($\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$). XRD measurements were performed from 2 theta 5° to 80° with 0.03° per 2 seconds. Black arrows indicate the appearance of important diffraction peaks for quartz (i.e. crystalline SiO_2). The most prominent SiO_2 peak (red line) is found between 2 theta of 26.48 and 26.78 and already indicative of the presence of SiO_2 when only 0.5% quartz dust was added. Note that, however, no quartz was detectable in any of the three forage samples.

Figure S2. Selection of 3DST parameters with best discrimination between feeding groups. Significance levels from Lincon test: 0.05 = *, 0.01 = **, 0.001 = *** confirmed by Cliff's Method. Thick horizontal bar represents the median; the box encloses the first (25%) and third (75%) quartiles; the whiskers (extend to 1.5 times the length of the box (the interquartile range); the unfilled dots represent outliers. *FLTp* = peak to reference flatness deviation (Gaussian Filter, 0.025 mm), *FLTv* = reference to valley flatness deviation (Gaussian Filter, 0.025 mm), *FLTt* = peak to valley flatness deviation of the surface (Gaussian Filter, 0.025 mm), *IsT* = texture isotropy, *metf* = mean depth of furrows, *medf* = mean density of furrows.

Figure S3. SEM image of A) timothy grass (*Phleum pratense*) phytoliths exposed after 3h by plasma etching showing typical parallel arrangement along the proximo-distal axis of the leaf; and B) bamboo (*Phyllostachys aureosulcata f. spectabilis*) after 9h with a higher density of silicified structures. Scale bar 50 μm.

Figure S4. Mean daily dry matter intake per feeding group measured over the course of four consecutive days.

Table S1. Nutrient composition of the forages used in this study

Forage	State	Dry matter	Crude protein	Neutral detergent fibre	Acid detergent fibre	Acid detergent lignin	Acid detergent insoluble ash	Hemi-cellulose	Cellulose	Lignin
		g / kg as fed	----- g / kg dry matter -----					- g / kg neutral detergent fibre -		
Lucerne ^a	fresh	166	218	660	398	92	4.7	397	464	139
	dry	918	206	665	428	76	3.9	356	530	114
Timothy grass ^b	fresh	232	168	707	310	43	5.8	562	377	62
	dry	930	170	703	354	35	6.7	496	453	50
Bamboo ^c	fresh	493	148	741	402	162	32.1	457	324	218
	dry	922	139	797	481	165	32.5	397	396	207

^a*Medicago sativa*; ^b*Phleum pratense*; ^c*Phyllostachys aureosulcata f. spectabilis*

Table S2. Description of applied surface texture parameters according to ISO 25178, ISO 12781, motif, furrow, texture direction and isotropy.

Parameter	Description (condition)	Standard	Unit
<i>S10z</i>	Ten-point height	ISO 25178	μm
<i>S5p</i>	Five-point peak height	ISO 25178	μm
<i>S5v</i>	Five-point valley height	ISO 25178	μm
<i>Sa</i>	Arithmetic mean height or mean surface roughness	ISO 25178	μm
<i>Sal</i>	Auto-correlation length ($s = 0.2$)	ISO 25178	μm
<i>Sda</i>	Closed dale area	ISO 25178	μm^2
<i>Sdq</i>	Root mean square gradient	ISO 25178	no unit
<i>Sdr</i>	Developed interfacial area ratio	ISO 25178	%
<i>Sdv</i>	Closed dale volume	ISO 25178	μm^3
<i>Sha</i>	Closed hill area	ISO 25178	μm^2
<i>Shv</i>	Closed hill volume	ISO 25178	μm^3
<i>Sku</i>	Kurtosis of the height distribution	ISO 25178	no unit
<i>Smc</i>	Inverse areal material ratio ($p = 10\%$)	ISO 25178	μm
<i>Smr</i>	Areal material ration, bearing area at given height ($c = 1 \mu\text{m}$ under the highest peak)	ISO 25178	μm
<i>Sp</i>	Maximum peak height, height between highest peak and mean plane	ISO 25178	μm
<i>Spc</i>	Arithmetic mean peak curvature	ISO 25178	$1/\mu\text{m}$
<i>Spd</i>	Density of peaks	ISO 25178	$1/\mu\text{m}^2$
<i>Sq</i>	Standard deviation of the height distribution, or RMS surface roughness	ISO 25178	μm
<i>Ssk</i>	Skewness of the height distribution	ISO 25178	no unit
<i>Std</i>	Texture direction	ISO 25178	–
<i>Str</i>	Texture aspect ratio ($s = 0.2$)	ISO 25178	no unit
<i>Sv</i>	Maximum pit height, depth between the mean plane and the deepest valley	ISO 25178	μm
<i>Sxp</i>	Peak extreme height difference between $p = 50\%$ and $q = 97.5\%$	ISO 25178	μm
<i>Sz</i>	Maximum height, height between the highest peak and the deepest valley	ISO 25178	μm
<i>Vm</i>	Material volume at a given material ratio ($p = 10\%$)	ISO 25178	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$
<i>Vmp</i>	Material volume of the peaks	ISO 25178	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$
<i>Vmc</i>	Material volume of the core at given material ratio ($p = 10\%$, $q = 80\%$)	ISO 25178	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$
<i>Vv</i>	Void volume at a given material ratio ($p = 10\%$)	ISO 25178	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$
<i>Vvc</i>	Void volume of the core ($p = 10\%$, $q = 80\%$)	ISO 25178	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$
<i>Vvv</i>	Void volume of the valley at a given material ratio ($p = 80\%$)	ISO 25178	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$
<i>nMotif</i>	Number of motifs	Motif	no unit
<i>meh</i>	Mean height	Motif	μm
<i>mea</i>	Mean area	Motif	μm^2
<i>madf</i>	Maximum depth of furrows	Furrow	μm
<i>metf</i>	Mean depth of furrows	Furrow	μm
<i>medf</i>	Mean density of furrows	Furrow	cm/cm^2
<i>Tr1R</i>	First direction	Direction	–
<i>Tr2R</i>	Second direction	Direction	–
<i>Tr3R</i>	Third direction	Direction	–
<i>IsT</i>	Texture isotropy	Isotropy	%

Parameter	Description (condition)	Standard	Unit
<i>FLTt</i>	Peak to valley flatness deviation of the surface (Gaussian Filter, 0.025 mm)	ISO 12781	μm
<i>FLTp</i>	Peak to reference flatness deviation (Gaussian Filter, 0.025 mm)	ISO 12781	μm
<i>FLTv</i>	Reference to valley flatness deviation (Gaussian Filter, 0.025 mm)	ISO 12781	μm
<i>FLTq</i>	Root mean square flatness deviation (Gaussian Filter, 0.025 mm)	ISO 12781	μm

Table S3. Descriptive statistics with mean and standard deviation (SD) of the 44 3DST parameters.

		<i>Bamboo dry</i>	<i>Bamboo fresh</i>	<i>Grass dry</i>	<i>Grass fresh</i>	<i>Lucerne dry</i>	<i>Lucerne fresh</i>
	n	6	5	6	6	6	6
<i>Sq</i>	Mean	0.459	0.489	0.355	0.224	0.262	0.255
	SD	0.045	0.112	0.023	0.034	0.039	0.035
<i>Ssk</i>	Mean	0.032	-0.334	-0.706	-0.918	-0.889	-0.978
	SD	0.116	0.479	0.272	0.275	0.296	0.188
<i>Sku</i>	Mean	2.764	4.163	4.588	4.339	4.186	4.506
	SD	0.147	1.143	0.949	0.821	0.951	0.521
<i>Sp</i>	Mean	1.453	2.240	1.152	0.535	0.649	0.622
	SD	0.156	1.692	0.379	0.085	0.099	0.209
<i>Sv</i>	Mean	1.529	2.467	1.644	0.931	1.061	1.059
	SD	0.282	0.863	0.273	0.136	0.184	0.111
<i>Sz</i>	Mean	3.001	4.950	2.923	1.464	1.683	1.679
	SD	0.293	2.379	0.620	0.212	0.266	0.299
<i>Sa</i>	Mean	0.373	0.379	0.271	0.172	0.203	0.195
	SD	0.037	0.081	0.020	0.029	0.031	0.026
<i>Smr</i>	Mean	19.282	17.569	43.975	95.142	88.847	86.468
	SD	5.882	16.773	28.793	3.242	8.145	19.522
<i>Smc</i>	Mean	0.603	0.601	0.407	0.257	0.298	0.278
	SD	0.062	0.147	0.036	0.043	0.042	0.035
<i>Sxp</i>	Mean	0.888	1.075	0.886	0.577	0.664	0.676
	SD	0.107	0.213	0.042	0.086	0.097	0.071
<i>Sal</i>	Mean	4.695	5.041	4.716	2.766	3.406	3.229
	SD	0.367	0.545	0.397	0.763	0.802	0.606
<i>Str</i>	Mean	0.385	0.467	0.666	0.490	0.561	0.491
	SD	0.026	0.071	0.079	0.113	0.113	0.100
<i>Std</i>	Mean	55.521	49.671	53.064	26.003	29.000	39.144
	SD	64.457	27.653	22.161	12.827	14.716	18.977
<i>Sdq</i>	Mean	0.365	0.481	0.383	0.289	0.286	0.302
	SD	0.066	0.214	0.101	0.064	0.017	0.036
<i>Sdr</i>	Mean	5.990	7.914	6.156	4.015	3.694	4.261
	SD	1.932	5.509	2.484	1.731	0.348	1.040
<i>Vm</i>	Mean	0.020	0.021	0.013	0.007	0.008	0.007
	SD	0.002	0.013	0.003	0.001	0.002	0.002
<i>Vv</i>	Mean	0.622	0.622	0.419	0.263	0.306	0.285
	SD	0.063	0.159	0.039	0.044	0.044	0.038
<i>Vmp</i>	Mean	0.020	0.021	0.013	0.007	0.008	0.007
	SD	0.002	0.013	0.003	0.001	0.002	0.002
<i>Vmc</i>	Mean	0.427	0.412	0.297	0.190	0.227	0.217
	SD	0.046	0.089	0.026	0.034	0.035	0.029
<i>Vvc</i>	Mean	0.574	0.551	0.363	0.228	0.264	0.243
	SD	0.058	0.156	0.041	0.039	0.040	0.033
<i>Vvv</i>	Mean	0.049	0.063	0.055	0.037	0.042	0.043
	SD	0.006	0.014	0.004	0.005	0.007	0.005

		Bamboo dry	Bamboo fresh	Grass dry	Grass fresh	Lucerne dry	Lucerne fresh
<i>Spd</i>	Mean	0.015	0.011	0.020	0.041	0.029	0.025
	SD	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.020	0.009	0.006
<i>Spc</i>	Mean	1.175	5.092	2.289	0.976	1.016	0.948
	SD	0.530	4.710	1.493	0.204	0.488	0.160
<i>S10z</i>	Mean	1.871	2.990	1.894	1.052	1.178	1.193
	SD	0.288	1.562	0.594	0.120	0.156	0.217
<i>S5p</i>	Mean	0.870	1.244	0.602	0.338	0.384	0.403
	SD	0.117	1.041	0.253	0.046	0.060	0.157
<i>S5v</i>	Mean	1.032	1.610	1.235	0.716	0.805	0.781
	SD	0.184	0.443	0.292	0.105	0.134	0.061
<i>Sda</i>	Mean	41.229	59.860	34.946	20.442	25.114	22.914
	SD	10.433	26.585	9.034	4.194	6.044	4.018
<i>Sha</i>	Mean	49.841	50.156	35.366	20.766	27.378	30.600
	SD	12.548	20.675	5.103	5.202	5.727	6.376
<i>Sdv</i>	Mean	0.680	1.383	0.758	0.351	0.444	0.403
	SD	0.052	0.729	0.124	0.054	0.158	0.107
<i>Shv</i>	Mean	1.471	1.425	0.761	0.311	0.476	0.483
	SD	0.553	0.578	0.195	0.072	0.165	0.133
<i>FLTt</i>	Mean	1.111	1.164	0.711	0.319	0.449	0.411
	SD	0.195	0.273	0.160	0.063	0.162	0.075
<i>FLTp</i>	Mean	0.531	0.630	0.357	0.152	0.199	0.175
	SD	0.096	0.162	0.123	0.035	0.068	0.030
<i>FLTv</i>	Mean	0.581	0.564	0.336	0.175	0.250	0.232
	SD	0.102	0.162	0.045	0.037	0.106	0.060
<i>FLTq</i>	Mean	0.265	0.261	0.145	0.071	0.101	0.096
	SD	0.064	0.046	0.047	0.018	0.038	0.016
<i>nMotif</i>	Mean	62.750	47.000	81.000	157.583	112.333	102.583
	SD	10.430	11.275	7.829	69.419	35.993	25.683
<i>meh</i>	Mean	0.309	0.562	0.258	0.147	0.162	0.157
	SD	0.019	0.339	0.054	0.021	0.018	0.032
<i>mea</i>	Mean	61.057	82.093	45.320	26.367	35.998	37.588
	SD	8.783	23.491	4.368	8.541	12.731	9.858
<i>madf</i>	Mean	1.462	2.098	1.477	1.053	1.157	1.207
	SD	0.187	0.856	0.278	0.099	0.146	0.130
<i>metf</i>	Mean	0.543	0.501	0.385	0.296	0.316	0.315
	SD	0.041	0.124	0.048	0.044	0.032	0.051
<i>medf</i>	Mean	4358.698	4424.329	4636.257	4695.435	4569.452	4571.388
	SD	204.179	336.426	167.958	260.761	76.643	108.871
<i>Tr1R</i>	Mean	8.256	22.275	34.452	15.085	21.669	45.049
	SD	12.655	16.748	23.216	11.587	16.414	11.764
<i>Tr2R</i>	Mean	39.446	61.166	51.854	30.783	47.215	29.757
	SD	18.488	43.173	18.703	14.689	22.441	14.693
<i>Tr3R</i>	Mean	31.601	33.045	42.842	44.943	38.188	33.772
	SD	10.547	16.376	13.123	15.511	21.616	12.583
<i>IsT</i>	Mean	26.379	43.748	66.487	45.791	53.773	50.008
	SD	5.315	14.243	7.894	8.414	8.265	11.100

Table S4. Significant differences in 3DST parameters between all feeding groups for Welch-Yuen, a pairwise comparison test (“Lincon test”, equivalent to Dunnett’s T3 test). Significances confirmed by Cliff’s Method are highlighted in green. Significance levels: 0.05 = *, 0.01 = **, 0.001 = ***, NS = not significant.

Parameter	Welch -Yuen Test	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Grass	Grass	Grass	Grass	Grass	Lucerne
		dry	dry	dry	dry	dry	fresh	fresh	fresh	fresh	dry	dry	dry	fresh	fresh	dry
		Bamboo fresh	Grass dry	Grass fresh	Lucerne dry	Lucerne fresh	Grass dry	Grass fresh	Lucerne dry	Lucerne fresh	Grass fresh	Lucerne dry	Lucerne fresh	Lucerne dry	Lucerne fresh	Lucerne fresh
<i>FLTp</i>	***	NS	*	***	***	***	*	**	**	**	**	NS	*	NS	NS	NS
<i>FLTq</i>	***	NS	**	***	***	***	**	***	***	***	**	NS	*	NS	*	NS
<i>FLTt</i>	***	NS	**	***	***	***	*	**	**	**	***	*	**	NS	*	NS
<i>FLTv</i>	***	NS	***	***	***	***	*	**	**	**	***	NS	**	NS	NS	NS
<i>IsT</i>	***	*	***	***	***	**	*	NS	NS	NS	***	*	*	NS	NS	NS
<i>madf</i>	**	NS	NS	***	**	*	NS	*	*	*	**	*	*	NS	NS	NS
<i>mea</i>	***	NS	**	***	**	***	*	**	**	**	**	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>medf</i>	NS	NS	***	***	***	***	NS	*	*	*	**	*	*	NS	NS	NS
<i>meh</i>	***	NS	NS	***	***	***	NS	NS	NS	NS	**	**	**	NS	NS	NS
<i>metf</i>	***	NS	*	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>nMotif</i>	***	*	**	*	*	*	**	*	**	**	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>S10z</i>	***	NS	NS	***	***	***	NS	*	NS	NS	*	*	*	NS	NS	NS
<i>S5p</i>	***	NS	NS	***	***	***	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>S5v</i>	**	*	NS	**	*	*	NS	**	*	*	**	*	*	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sa</i>	***	NS	***	***	***	***	*	**	**	**	***	**	***	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sal</i>	***	NS	NS	***	**	***	NS	***	**	***	***	**	***	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sda</i>	**	NS	NS	**	*	**	NS	*	*	*	**	NS	*	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sdq</i>	NS	NS	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sdr</i>	NS	NS	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sdv</i>	***	NS	NS	***	*	***	NS	*	*	*	***	**	***	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sha</i>	***	NS	*	***	**	*	NS	*	NS	NS	**	*	NS	NS	*	NS

Parameter	Welch -Yuen Test	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Bamboo	Grass	Grass	Grass	Grass	Grass	Lucerne
		dry	dry	dry	dry	dry	fresh	fresh	fresh	fresh	fresh	dry	dry	dry	fresh	fresh
		Bamboo	Grass	Grass	Lucerne	Lucerne	Grass	Grass	Lucerne	Lucerne	Grass	Lucerne	Lucerne	Lucerne	Lucerne	Lucerne
		fresh	dry	fresh	dry	fresh	dry	fresh	dry	fresh	fresh	dry	fresh	dry	fresh	fresh
<i>Shv</i>	***	NS	*	**	**	**	NS	*	*	*	**	*	*	NS	*	NS
<i>Sku</i>	***	NS	**	**	*	***	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>Smc</i>	***	NS	***	***	***	***	*	**	**	**	***	***	***	NS	NS	NS
<i>Smr</i>	***	NS	NS	***	***	***	NS	***	***	***	**	*	*	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sp</i>	***	NS	NS	***	***	***	NS	NS	NS	NS	**	*	*	NS	NS	NS
<i>Spc</i>	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>Spd</i>	***	NS	*	*	*	**	***	*	**	***	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sq</i>	***	NS	***	***	***	***	NS	**	**	**	***	***	***	NS	NS	NS
<i>Ssk</i>	***	NS	***	***	***	***	NS	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>Std</i>	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
<i>Str</i>	***	NS	***	NS	*	*	**	NS	NS	NS	*	NS	**	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sv</i>	***	NS	NS	**	**	**	NS	*	*	*	***	**	**	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sxp</i>	***	NS	NS	***	**	**	NS	**	**	*	***	***	***	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sz</i>	***	NS	NS	***	***	***	NS	*	*	*	***	**	**	NS	NS	NS
<i>Tr1R</i>	**	NS	*	NS	NS	***	NS	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	***	NS
<i>Tr2R</i>	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	NS
<i>Tr3R</i>	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	***	NS	NS	NS	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	***	*
<i>Vm</i>	***	NS	***	***	***	***	NS	NS	NS	NS	***	**	**	NS	NS	NS
<i>Vmc</i>	***	NS	***	***	***	***	*	**	**	**	***	**	***	NS	NS	NS
<i>Vmp</i>	***	NS	***	***	***	***	NS	NS	NS	NS	**	**	**	NS	NS	NS
<i>Vv</i>	***	NS	***	***	***	***	*	**	**	**	***	***	***	NS	NS	NS
<i>Vvc</i>	***	NS	***	***	***	***	NS	**	*	**	***	**	***	NS	NS	NS
<i>Vvv</i>	***	NS	NS	**	NS	NS	NS	**	*	*	***	**	***	NS	NS	NS

Additional data table S1 (separate file)

Raw 3D surface texture data of all 44 employed parameters for each individual surface texture scan.